

Proceedings of the
6th Educational Data Mining in Computer
Science Education (CSEDM) Workshop

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July 2022

Citation: Bitra Akram, Thomas Price, Yang Shi, Peter Brusilovsky, Sharon I-Han Hsiao,; Proceedings of 6th Educational Data Mining in Computer Science Education (CSEDM) Workshop. July 27, 2022, Durham, United Kingdom (2022).

This volume¹ represents the proceedings of the selected papers of the 6th Educational Data Mining in Computer Science Education (CSEDM) Workshop (CSEDM 2022), held on July 27, 2022².

The objective of the CSEDM workshop series is to facilitate a discussion among the research community at the intersection of Educational Data Mining (EDM), AI and Computer Science Education. The workshops are interdisciplinary events, designed to bring this community together to share insights for how to support and understand learning in the domain of CS using data. Researchers, faculty and students present data mining approaches, methodologies and experiences where AI is transforming the way students learn Computer Science (CS) skills.

CSEDM received 6 submissions to the full papers track, of which 3 were accepted (50%), while a further 2 were accepted as Work-In-Progress papers. There were 7 submissions to the short paper track, of which 5 were accepted (71.4%). The abstract track also accepted 1 additional submission. Each paper was peer reviewed by our program committee in a double-blinded way and decisions were made based on these reviews, as well as discussions by the workshop organizers.

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²Workshop website: <https://sites.google.com/ncsu.edu/csedm-workshop-edm22/home>

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